

Lessons in Statistics from ChatGPT

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Abstract

Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (or ChatGPT) is a large language model (LLM) that has been trained to answer questions in human-like dialogue form. It has been used to debug code, write recommendation letters, and even write research papers. As a result, its use has been of concern to the academic community. The round table “Lessons in Statistics from ChatGPT” met on August 8, 2023, with 5 participants: Patrick Bowman, Yifan Li, Thomas Messer, Taseneem Zaihra Rizvi, and Monnie McGee, in attendance. We discussed ways that ChatGPT can be used to generate questions (and answers) for important statistics concepts. These questions can be used as homework problems or on exams. We also discussed other ways to utilize ChatGPT in statistics courses and parameters around allowing students to use it. While we acknowledge the existence of other Generative AI/LLMs like Anthropic’s Claude and Google’s Bard, most of our discussion centered on ChatGPT. It is open source and the one with which most of us had experience. It should be noted that in the following, we use “ChatGPT” to refer to all Generative AI/ Large Language Model (LLM) software unless otherwise noted.

Key Words: Generative AI, classroom activities, statistics and data science education, academic integrity

1. ChatGPT states concerns about ChatGPT

Before the round table convened, the organizer (Monnie McGee) asked ChatGPT 3.5 “What concerns do professors at the college level have about using ChatGPT in the classroom?”. Chat GPT gave the following detailed response.

As of my last update in September 2021, using AI language models like ChatGPT in the college-level classroom was a relatively new and evolving practice. Professors may have had various concerns about incorporating such technology into their teaching methods. Here are some potential concerns they might have had:

1. **Academic Integrity and Plagiarism:** Professors might worry that students could misuse ChatGPT to generate plagiarized content for assignments or exams, making it difficult to assess students' true understanding and work.
2. **Quality and Accuracy of Responses:** AI language models are not infallible and can sometimes generate incorrect or misleading information. Professors might be concerned that students could unknowingly receive or rely on inaccurate answers, leading to misunderstandings or incorrect conclusions.
3. **Lack of Original Thought and Critical Thinking:** Relying heavily on AI-generated responses could discourage students from developing their critical thinking skills and limit their ability to formulate original ideas.
4. **Overreliance on Technology:** There might be concerns that students could become overly dependent on AI language models and neglect traditional research methods or classroom discussions.
5. **Ethical and Bias Issues:** AI language models can reflect and amplify biases present in the training data. Professors might worry about the ethical implications of using AI that could unintentionally perpetuate stereotypes or misinformation.
6. **Engagement and Interpersonal Skills:** Some educators might argue that using AI in the classroom could diminish opportunities for face-to-face interactions, discussions, and collaborative learning experiences.
7. **Lack of Personalized Feedback:** While AI can provide quick responses, it may not offer personalized feedback tailored to individual students' learning needs as effectively as human instructors can.
8. **Technical Challenges and Reliability:** Professors might be concerned about potential technical issues, such as internet connectivity problems or the AI model not providing responses as expected during class.
9. **Intellectual Property and Data Privacy:** If professors and students use a third-party AI tool, there might be concerns about the ownership of the generated content and the privacy of students' data.
10. **Preparation and Adaptation:** Adopting new technology in the classroom requires preparation and adaptation from instructors. Professors might worry about the time and effort needed to effectively integrate ChatGPT into their teaching practices.

It is worth noting that over time, as AI technology evolves and becomes more prevalent, these concerns may be addressed through improved AI models, better guidelines for use, and the development of best practices for incorporating AI into education. (ChatGPT 3.5, accessed July 25, 2023)

As an aside, ChatGPT is generally quite wordy, unless it is asked to provide a brief explanation. Therefore, those wishing for brief explanations should qualify requests to ChatGPT with something like “In less than 200 words ...” or “In 5 sentences ...”.

Round Table participants were provided with a copy of ChatGPT’s warnings against itself. One of the things the participants noted is the similarity in arguments produced by ChatGPT with older arguments against the use of calculators in the classroom, and, some years later, against the use of laptops in the classroom. Arguments against use of calculators and laptops centered around loss of ability to think critically and

discouragement of original thinking (Perry, 2017; Ravizza, 2017). Just as was done with calculators and laptops, some educators want to forbid use of LLMs in the classroom. Others want to encourage their use, and there is a spectrum of opinions in between. Arguments about using calculators and laptops in the classroom subsided after a few years, outweighed by a noticeable decrease in cognitive load for mundane tasks which freed up brain space for more creative efforts (Hembree and Dessart, 1986; Salomon, et. al., 1991). We suspect that something similar will happen with ChatGPT and other LLMs. Furthermore, banning the use of technology in the classroom will become increasingly difficult and futile as technology advances (Perry, 2017). As a result, research on the proper use of such technologies is more important than arguments about banning them.

While the Round Table participants did not touch on all the topics mentioned by ChatGPT, we specifically discussed the following: other technologies and plugins to use with ChatGPT, uses for ChatGPT in the classroom, catching overuse and misuse, making it hard to cheat with ChatGPT, and statistical issues that are raised by LLMs and Generative AI. We begin with the use of ChatGPT in the classroom because that was the original intention of the round table discussion.

2. Uses of ChatGPT in the Classroom

The main topic of discussion was appropriate use of ChatGPT in the classroom by catering to its strengths and using it to support tasks that are difficult to teach and learn. One such task is coding. There are two main uses for ChatGPT in the coding realm: one is taking pseudocode or a set-by-step algorithm and translating it into usable code, and another is translating between coding languages. While experience dictates that ChatGPT is not good with SAS code, ChatGPT can take working R code and create working Python code, and vice-versa. It can also take a set of instructions and create usable R or Python code. For example, when asked “Create a simulation for the Central Limit Theorem using R Code”, ChatGPT replied with the following code:

```
# Set the parameters for the population distribution
population_mean <- 50
population_sd <- 10
population_size <- 10000

# Generate a random population from a normal distribution
population <- rnorm(population_size, mean =
population_mean, sd = population_sd)

# Number of samples to draw from the population
num_samples <- 1000

# Sample size for each sample
sample_size <- 30

# Create an empty vector to store sample means
sample_means <- numeric(num_samples)

# Generate samples and calculate their means
for (i in 1:num_samples) {
  sample <- sample(population, size = sample_size)
  sample_means[i] <- mean(sample)
```

```

}

# Plot a histogram of the sample means
hist(sample_means, breaks = 30, main = "Distribution of
Sample Means",
      xlab = "Sample Mean", ylab = "Frequency", col =
"blue")

# Add a red curve representing the theoretical normal
distribution
curve(dnorm(x, mean = population_mean, sd =
population_sd/sqrt(sample_size)),
      col = "red", lwd = 2, add = TRUE)

```

It should be noted that the comments are from ChatGPT itself. The fact that it comments its own code is already a step beyond what most students (and professors) do! ChatGPT also helpfully added a definition of the CLT, and some instructions, “You can adjust the parameters (e.g., `population_mean`, `population_sd`, `population_size`, `num_samples`, `sample_size`) to see how the CLT works for different scenarios.” (ChatGPT 3.5, accessed September 21, 2023).

We ran the code in R 4.3.1 (R Core Team, 2023). The code produced a blue histogram of the means of sample means of size 30 from a Normal distribution with mean 50 and standard deviation 10. The histogram was bell-shaped, and calculation of the mean and standard deviation of the `sample_means` vector produced the anticipated results.

At the same time, we noticed some mistakes. First, ChatGPT generated a “population” of 10000 random normal random variables and drew samples from this vector to demonstrate the Central Limit Theorem. While 10000 is large, it is not infinite, and the CLT applies to infinite populations. Secondly, ChatGPT attempted to plot a red Normal density curve over the blue histogram of sample means, but the curve did not fit. The problem is that the y-axis for the density curve is on a scale of 0 to 1, while the y-axis for the histogram function in R is on a scale of the number of observations within each histogram bin (a frequency scale). ChatGPT did not seem to know about the “`probs = TRUE`” option in the `hist` function in R that would change the y-axis of the histogram to have a scale of 0 to 1. An instructor can use code such as this to illustrate the Central Limit Theorem while discussing the inaccuracies of the code. Another idea would be to give the ChatGPT-generated code to the students and ask them to correct it as necessary. Such an exercise would require students to have some facility with the code and would teach them that ChatGPT is fallible.

Other ideas for using ChatGPT in class include obtaining code for standard data sets for standard analyses. For example, when prompted with “Please show me R Code to analyze Fisher’s Iris Data”, ChatGPT replied with code to load the data set, code to perform exploratory data analysis using `ggplot` from the `tidyverse` package, code for statistical analysis using `aov` from the base package, and code for classification using `createDataPartitions` from the package `caret`. Interestingly, the code was not generated directly from R’s online help files for these functions. Further investigation revealed that ChatGPT obtained some of its code from StackOverflow without attribution.

1.1 Creating homework and exams

Round Table participants also discussed the use of ChatGPT for creating homework and exams. Notably, these are tasks that reduce cognitive load for professors and not students. For example, an instructor can enter a question prompt multiple times to get an idea of how students might respond to a given question. The instructor can even ask ChatGPT to give an incorrect, but plausible, answer, in order to create distractors for multiple choice or matching questions. Assignments can also be created to modify or annotate code generated by ChatGPT to teach basic coding or to troubleshoot basic code.

Instructors might worry about students using ChatGPT for essay exams. One way around this is to input example exam questions into ChatGPT to generate several sample answers to check against student work. In addition, because ChatGPT is a text-based editor is not designed to answer questions about visualizations. One can create an exam based entirely off answering questions about graphics and visualizations, or about creating such visualizations. For the latter, keep in mind that ChatGPT can generate working code for many visualizations.

1.2 Catching misuse and overuse

One of the main concerns for many educators is the misuse of ChatGPT. We have already discussed several ways that ChatGPT can be incorrect. As LLMs get better and better, it's possible that such mistakes will become less frequent. In addition, distinguishing human-generated content from AI-generated content will become more difficult. Current plagiarism detection algorithms are easily fooled by generative AI and produce both false-negative and false-positive results. Often, ChatGPT can pass the plagiarism detectors better than humans can (Kahalil and Er, 2023).

Educators are also concerned about students using ChatGPT to cheat on exams, particularly those that are given online. Some suggestions from the round table to make cheating with ChatGPT more difficult are

1. Use layered questions. Layered questions are those for which there is a prompt with several questions following the prompts that are related to it. Engineering a prompt for a layered question in ChatGPT takes some practice. A student working under time pressure might not be able to manage it effectively.
2. Ask questions about visualizations. ChatGPT 3.5 cannot interpret visualizations because it is text-based. ChatGPT 4 says it can interpret visualizations, but it does not do well that the task (personal experience). There are likely other LLMs that can interpret visualizations, but these were not investigated.
3. Ask questions about things that ChatGPT cannot access. For example, ChatGPT does not know class culture of a particular classroom. It does not know what examples might have been presented in class. It also might not know what is on the class syllabus.
4. Set a timer for the exam. Copying and pasting prompts into ChatGPT is somewhat time consuming. If an exam is properly timed, students will not be able to make much use of ChatGPT.
5. Give the exam using a paper and pencil, if at all possible.

These suggestions are not meant to be a comprehensive list. As the use of ChatGPT and other generative AI models grows, there will be more (and better)

ways to use them legitimately in the classroom. One thing is clear: these models are here to stay, and ignoring them or banning them will mean that students will not have proper guidance to use them appropriately.

1.3 Add-Ins and Limitations

In this section, we mention Excel and PDF plug-ins for ChatGPT. There are many such plug-ins, and many of them are useful for increasing productivity and reducing cognitive load on humans. We also discuss the limitations of ChatGPT and the necessity of good prompt engineering. These topics were not explored in detail during the round table. They are listed here because they were mentioned and deserve some discussion. These topics are relevant for use in the classroom as well as for more general use.

1.3.1 Excel and PDF Add-Ins

There are several plug-ins that can be used with ChatGPT that could be put to classroom use. First, there is ChatGPT excel. This comes in three flavors: as an Excel plugin for ChatGPT, an Excel macro for ChatGPT, and an Excel function for ChatGPT. The Excel macro allows the user to use human-like commands to obtain Excel output. For example, the user can ask Excel to perform a linear regression given certain data. The add-in will take the text commands and generate Excel commands. The Excel plug-in for ChatGPT will access Excel when the user asks for certain procedures using Excel (Bhalla, 2023).

There are other add-ins for working with PDF files in ChatGPT. One is Ai PDF, which allows the summarization of large PDF files. Another is MixerBox ChatPDF, which takes as input a URL address to a PDF file (Gwaro, 2023). It can also summarize the PDF in an efficient manner. Gwaro lists eight other PDF plug-ins and their capabilities. Without a PDF plugin to ChatGPT, the user is limited to typing (or copying and pasting) questions or commands into ChatGPT's input box. PDF plug-ins facilitate the reading of entire PDF documents. One of the impediments to use of ChatGPT for exams, for example, is that the student must type each question of the exam separately, which can take a great deal of time, particularly for a 50-minute exam. PDF plugins might bypass this requirement. As of the date of the round table, none of the participants had tried using one of these plug-ins to read an entire PDF file into ChatGPT.

1.3.2 Limitations of ChatGPT

One limitation of ChatGPT is its access to material. Clearly, there are copyright issues with some material, and Chat GPT does not reference its sources properly. As mentioned earlier, the R code for the analysis of Fisher's Iris Data was grabbed from StackOverflow without attribution. Furthermore, some of the ChatGPT's material is out of date. As of the writing of this manuscript, ChatGPT's database is current to 2021. However, there is a Chrome plug-in to update ChatGPT for current websites (ChatGPT for Google Chrome, available from the Chrome Web Store).

Finally, the group discussed prompt engineering and reverse engineering. These are more limitations for the user rather than for ChatGPT. Prompt engineering refers to the creation of prompts to elicit the information that a user wants from ChatGPT. The first attempt at a prompt usually results in more information than necessary, and fine-tuning of prompts is an iterative process, much like fine-tuning of search terms for a web browser. Reverse engineering refers to entering an answer into ChatGPT in order to determine the prompt that generated it. This can be useful for wording exam questions, or determining whether

certain exam questions might have been entered into ChatGPT to obtain a student's answer on a homework assignment or exam.

2. What can statisticians contribute to Large Language Models?

While many of the current questions around use of ChatGPT in education regard how to catch students when they are improperly using it, there are also many interesting statistical questions that can lead to development of statistical methods. Here are some that we posited:

1. One suggestion for creating assignments or catching students when they use ChatGPT is to enter the same question into ChatGPT multiple times. Each time, ChatGPT will give a slightly different answer. This begs the question about how many times should one enter a question into ChatGPT to get a representative sample of answers.
2. How would one measure "effect size" when the response is text for the purposes of sample size and power calculation for experiments where a covariate or a response is text?
3. ChatGPT can generate R code. Do we really need to create R packages anymore for new methodology? Would not having R packages lead to more or a reproducibility crisis? It can be a great deal of trouble to reproduce analyses even when step by step instructions or code exist. Can ChatGPT be used to aid individuals in writing reproducible code?
4. LLMs are based on probabilistic prediction of the next word. What algorithms are they using? What are the statistical or mathematical properties of these algorithms?
5. ChatGPT results can be misleading and non-representative of past and present work in certain areas. Statisticians can be useful in creating "reward functions" that assign a numeric probability or index score to an answer in ChatGPT. The score is an indicator of the trustworthiness of ChatGPT's answer or of the representativeness of the results.

Indeed, some of these ideas were discussed at JSM in late breaking sessions and other sessions sponsored by the Section on Text Analysis. Round table participants suggest examining proceedings articles from these sessions for further detail on how statisticians can contribute to research on LLMs and AI.

3. Further Resources and Conclusion

The group mentioned a series of articles in the *New York Times* technology section on Deep Learning and AI (Roose, 2023). Because AI is changing at breakneck speed, a daily newspaper such as the *New York Times* is a good source for regular updates and continuing discussion. There are also hackathons that have sprung up to test various aspects of generative AI models. In particular, the annual hackathon DEFCON held in Las Vegas, NV, tasks users with getting generative AI models to breach security or otherwise behave badly.

This article has focused on the use of generative AI inside the classroom. It is worth noting that there are many uses for generative AI outside the classroom. For example, ChatGPT can be used for health and medical transcription (Khan, et.al, 2023). It can take complicated medical terms and translate them into plain English. It can also summarize documents and aid in finding references for various ideas. Of course, the medical terms,

transcriptions, translations, and references should always be checked for veracity and validity. In the absence of something to answer, ChatGPT has been known to make stuff up (O'Brien, 2023). To its credit, however, when asked for scholarly references on reduction of cognitive load with calculators in the classroom, ChatGPT politely replied, "I apologize, but I cannot provide direct access to specific scholarly references as my knowledge is not linked to external databases or the internet. However, I can suggest a general approach for finding scholarly references on these topics. To find scholarly references on reducing cognitive load with the use of calculators in the classroom and laptops, you can follow these steps:" (asked October 8, 2023) and proceeded to list some good pointers on searching for references on the Internet, including accessing academic databases and asking a librarian.

With the advent of generative AI, statisticians and data scientists might be worried that our services are no longer required. However, it is important to note that, in addition to the areas of research listed in this article, statisticians can provide output and model interpretation, additional creativity, and methodology checking beyond what generative AI can provide. After all, ChatGPT cannot see the big picture of an analysis or coding exercise. It does not understand the aims of the researcher (for better or worse). Chat GPT does not understand data provenance and cannot incorporate such things into an analysis. Furthermore, it cannot express the nuances of an analysis. As use of AI grows, so must input into its proper use and limitations from statisticians grow.

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